

Exploring the Antitubercular potential of Pyrazole scaffold based Thiazolidinones: Design, In-Silico Evaluation and Synthetic strategies

Sonia George, Indhumathi S., Karthikeyan M., Thamarapriya G., Nandhini S., Gayathri Senbagam V.*

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore-641044, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, remains one of the leading infectious diseases worldwide due to the emergence of multidrug-resistance. The discovery and design of novel antitubercular drugs are focused on attractive biological targets Enoyl-acyl-carrier protein-reductase (InhA), β -ketoacyl-ACP reductase (MabA) and Pantothenate kinase (PanK) enzymes. The leads were selected by virtual screening using iGEMDOCKv2.1 and optimised by Molinspiration server for drug – likeness and pharmacokinetic profile by QikProp, Schrodinger showed that none of the compounds were toxic and was predicted to have good oral bioavailability. Network pharmacology and molecular docking analyses were performed to identify potential molecular targets of the synthesized compounds. Gene Ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment analyses were performed using Shiny GO. Molecular docking studies revealed that among the designed leads, PTH 8 and PTH 1 demonstrated the highest binding affinity against the InhA enzyme, with docking scores of -7.802 and -7.668 kcal/mol, respectively in comparison with standard triclosan -6.146 kcal/mol. The molecular dynamic studies revealed the stability of ligand- protein complexes. The synthesized compounds were characterized using UV–Visible, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and mass spectroscopy. The antitubercular activity was evaluated by microplate alamar blue assay method showed that the compounds PTH 8 (-4-OCH₃), PTH 9 (-4-CH₃) had shown excellent minimum inhibitory concentration at 1.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ which is same as standard isoniazid. Among the synthesized compounds, methoxy substituted pyrazolyl thiazole was found to be potent enzyme inhibitors due to superior docking and biological activity results.

Keywords: Tuberculosis; Pyrazolyl derivatives; Thiazolidinone; Network pharmacology; Molecular docking.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB), historically referred to as “consumption” or the “white death,” is an infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [1]. It primarily affects the lungs but may also involve extrapulmonary organs. TB can remain latent (latent tuberculosis infection, LTBI) and become active under favourable conditions. Approximately 5–10% of latent infections progress to active disease during a lifetime [2]. The disease spreads through airborne droplets generated by coughing or sneezing of infected individuals. Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major global health concern. According to the World Health Organization Global Tuberculosis Report

2025, TB continues to be one of the leading causes of death from a single infectious agent worldwide [2]. In 2024, an estimated 10.7 million people developed TB globally, including 5.8 million men, 3.7 million women, and about 1.2million children and adolescents. Globally, TB caused approximately 1.23 million deaths in 2024, including around 150,000 deaths among people living with HIV [2]. Despite being a preventable and curable disease, TB continues to impose a significant global health burden [3]. Current treatment requires prolonged multidrug therapy using first-line anti-tubercular agents such as isoniazid, rifampicin, and pyrazinamide, which may

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

lead to adverse drug reactions and poor patient adherence [4]. These limitations have contributed to the emergence of drug-resistant strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, including multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB), extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB), and totally drug-resistant TB (TDR-TB), which are resistant to multiple first and second-line drugs and require longer, more complex, and costly treatment regimens [5].

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is a slow-growing, non-motile bacillus with a generation time of 12–20 hours and may require several weeks for visible growth on culture media. It possesses a lipid-rich cell wall containing mycolic acids, which confer resistance to conventional staining methods; therefore, acid-fast staining is employed. The organism is strictly aerobic and capable of surviving under adverse environmental conditions. Although *M. tuberculosis* is the main cause of TB in humans, other species such as *Mycobacterium bovis*, *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium microti*, *Mycobacterium canettii*, *Mycobacterium caprae*, and *Mycobacterium pinnipedii* can also cause the disease [6].

Network pharmacology has emerged as a powerful approach for understanding the complex interactions between drugs, targets, and diseases at a systems level [7]. Unlike traditional “one drug–one target” strategies, network pharmacology integrates bioinformatics, systems biology, and pharmacology to elucidate multi-target mechanisms of therapeutic agents. This approach is particularly valuable in the treatment of complex diseases such as tuberculosis, where multiple biological pathways and host–pathogen interactions are involved. In recent years, network pharmacology has been widely applied in drug discovery to identify potential targets, predict pharmacological mechanisms, and explore synergistic effects of compounds. By combining target prediction databases such as Swiss Target Prediction with disease-related gene databases like Gene Cards, it is possible to identify overlapping targets that may play a critical role in disease modulation [8]. Furthermore, protein–protein interaction (PPI) network analysis enables the identification of hub genes that are essential for disease progression and therapeutic intervention. Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG)

pathway enrichment analyses further provide insights into the biological processes, molecular functions, and signalling pathways associated with these targets. These analyses help in understanding how compounds may regulate immune responses, inflammatory pathways, and cellular signalling mechanisms involved in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection.

Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations are a computational method that uses Newton's laws to analyze the movements of water, ions, small molecules, and complex systems like whole viruses. It is used to replicate the behavior of biological environments, including water molecules and lipid membranes. Specifically, it helps to study the structural motions that depend on temperature and solute/solvent, which is crucial for understanding the recognition pattern of ligand-protein or protein-protein complexes. MD simulations are useful because they can model these motions efficiently. MD simulations are also incredibly beneficial for drug design. They can provide insights into the structural cavities required to design novel structures with higher affinity to the target. Additionally, they can refine the three-dimensional (3D) structure of targets to obtain a better sampling of the binding poses and more reliable affinity values. Traditional docking procedures do not incorporate biological conditions that include structural motions, which is where MD simulations excel. This work analyzes the concepts and applicability of MD simulations for drug design, with a focus on molecular structural motions. These motions help to identify hot spots, decipher structural details in the reported protein sites, and eliminate any structural artifacts that could be caused by the MD's structural characterization conditions.^{[9][10]}

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Phase I: *In Silico* studies

1. Drug Target Selection

Enoyl ACP reductase, Beta ketoacyl ACP reductase and Pantothenate kinase of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) was selected as the drug targets from the literature support. The enzymes were retrieved from RCSB protein data bank. 1) Mtb Enoyl ACP reductase is encoded by the gene expression

InhA (PDB ID: 2B35) bound to triclosan 2) Mtb β -ketoacyl ACP reductase is encoded by the gene expression MabA (PDB ID: 1UZN) in apo form 3) Mtb Pantothenate kinase is encoded by the gene expression PanK (PDB ID: 4BFZ) bound to 2-[4-(4-cyanophenyl)-3-{{4-(pyridin-2-yl)piperazin-1-yl}methyl}phenoxy]-n-methyl acetamide

2. Lead identification by Virtual Screening

Virtual screening is a computational technique used in drug discovery to search libraries of small molecules to identify those structures which are most likely to bind to a drug target, typically a protein receptor or enzyme. It is generally used for the selection of the lead from hits. Virtual screening was done by using iGEMDOCKv.2. Using PubChem, the free data base of around thirteen million commercially available compounds, a small molecule library consisting of 25 compounds were constructed. The proteins with the accession code (PDB ID) 2B35, 1UZN & 4BFZ corresponding to Enoyl ACP reductase, β -ketoacyl ACP reductase and Pantothenate kinase of *M. tuberculosis* were selected from the RCSB protein data bank.

3. Lead optimisation

Based on the virtual screening and literature review, the lead molecule is identified. The identified lead molecule is optimized by lead optimization. Lead optimization was done by evaluating the Drug likeness potential and ADME screening. Computation of Drug likeness potential of the designed leads was screened by molinspiration and qikprop. The drug-likeness score will help to evaluate the better oral absorption of the ligands. The score includes solubility, diffusion, Log P, hydrogen bond acceptors, hydrogen bond donors, molecular weight, etc. One of the ideal methods for this is using Lipinski's rule of five with the molinspiration server. The ADME studies performed by using Schrodinger Maestro v13.1, Qik Prop will help in the computational evaluation of the ADME scores.

4. Network pharmacology

Drug Target Prediction: Potential molecular targets of the synthesized compounds were predicted using the **SwissTargetPrediction** database based on their

SMILES structures. Only targets with high probability scores were selected. Tuberculosis-associated genes were retrieved from the **Gene Cards** database and filtered using relevance scores to obtain disease-specific targets^[8]. To ensure the specificity of the disease landscape, genes were filtered based on their Relevance Score, ensuring a robust set of disease-specific proteins for downstream analysis.

Intersection Analysis: Intersection analysis was performed using the **Venny 2.1** platform to identify overlapping targets between compound-related and disease-associated genes. These common targets were considered potential therapeutic targets and used for further protein-protein interaction analysis^[11].

Construction of protein-protein interaction network: Protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks were constructed using the **STRING database (version 12.0)** to evaluate functional associations among target proteins^[12]. The network was further analysed using **Cytoscape** software to identify hub genes based on topological parameters such as degree centrality^[13].

GO and KEGG pathway analysis: Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG pathway enrichment analyses were performed using the ShinyGO platform^[14]. GO terms were categorized into **Biological Process, Molecular Function, and Cellular Component**^[15]. Pathway enrichment was analysed through the KEGG pathway database. The top enriched pathways were selected based on significance and visualized using SR plot^[16,17,18].

5. Molecular docking studies

Drug targets were selected based on literature reports and structural availability in the **RCSB Protein Data Bank**. Three key enzymes of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* involved in essential metabolic pathways were chosen: enoyl-ACP reductase, β -ketoacyl-ACP reductase, and pantothenate kinase. These protein structures were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank, including InhA (2B35), MabA (1UZN), and PanK (4BFZ). These proteins were selected as potential targets for evaluating the binding interactions of the synthesized compounds. Molecular docking studies were carried out using the Glide

module of Schrödinger Maestro to evaluate ligand–protein interactions.

6. Molecular Dynamics Studies

The stability of the docking compounds were examined utilizing academic Desmond software. All *in silico* studies were carried out in the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, SRIPMS, College of Pharmacy, and Coimbatore.

Phase II: Synthetic Studies

Based on molecular docking results and synthetic feasibility, compounds with favourable docking

scores and strong ligand–target interactions were selected for synthesis using conventional methods.

Chemicals and Reagents: Acetophenone, phenyl hydrazine, aniline, 4-nitroaniline, 4-chloroaniline, 4-bromoaniline, 4-fluoroaniline, xylydine, 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline, *p*-anisidine, *p*-aminobenzoic acid, and 4-methylaniline were used as starting materials. Solvents and reagents included ethanol, glacial acetic acid, dimethylformamide, phosphorus oxychloride, thioglycolic acid, chloroacetyl chloride, and acetone. All chemicals were procured from Sigma-Aldrich, Loba Chemie, and S.D. Fine Chemicals and were used without further purification.

Scheme 1

Step 1: Synthesis of 1-phenyl -2- (1-phenylethylidene) hydrazine^[19]: Acetophenone (0.01mol) was dissolved in 10ml of ethanol containing few drops of glacial acetic acid, and phenyl hydrazine (0.01mol) was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hours. On completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled in room temperature. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Step 2: Synthesis of 1,4- diphenyl-1H- pyrazole -3- carbaldehyde^[19]: N,N- dimethyl formamide (0.02 mol) was taken in a 250 ml round bottom flask, cooled at 0-5°C and phosphorous oxychloride (0.01mol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir at the same temperature for 30 mins and ((2Z) –

1-phenyl -2- (1-phenylethylidene) hydrazine) was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to stir at room temperature and refluxed for 6 hrs. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured with continuous stirring onto cold water and filtered off, washed with cold water. The obtained precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Step 3: Synthesis of 1- (1,3- diphenyl -1H- pyrazol- 4yl) –N- phenyl methanimine (PYR 1-10)^[19]: Substituted anilines (0.005 mol) were dissolved in 30 ml of ethanol and 0.9 ml of glacial acetic acid was added. Pyrazole aldehyde (0.005 mol) was added to the above mixture and was refluxed for 6 hrs. After cooling, the mixture was added to crushed ice by

stirring. The separated product was filtered, washed, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol. **Scheme 2**

Synthesis of 2-(1, 3-diphenyl -1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-3 phenyl-1, 3-thiazolidin-4-one (PTH₁₋₁₀)^[20](E) -1-(1, 3- diphenyl -1H- pyrazol-4yl) -N- phenyl methanimine (0.001mol) treated with mercaptoacetic acid (Thioglycolic acid) (0.002mol) in dioxane 25ml in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride and reaction

mixture was refluxed for 4 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured in crushed ice with stirring. Thus the separated solid was then filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate to remove unreacted thioglycolic acid and recrystallized from ethanol.

Table 1: Chemical substituents of PTH (PTH₁₋₁₀) derivatives

COMPOUND CODE	R	COMPOUND CODE	R
PTH 1	-4 H	PTH 6	-2, 6-CH ₃
PTH 2	-4 NO ₂	PTH 7	-4 F
PTH 3	-4 Br	PTH 8	-4 OCH ₃
PTH 4	-4 Cl	PTH 9	-4 CH ₃
PTH 5	-3 Cl, -4 F	PTH 10	-4 COOH

Phase III: Analytical characterisation

Physicochemical Parameters such as Solubility, Melting Point analysis by Visible Range melting point apparatus (LABINDIA), Thin Layer Chromatography were performed for the synthesized compounds. Characterization of the synthesized compounds was performed by UV spectroscopy, Infrared spectroscopy, MASS spectroscopy on JASCO V-530, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, SRIPMS, COP, Coimbatore. ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy was recorded on 300 MHz BRUKER, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore.

Phase IV: Antimycobacterial Screening

All the synthesized compounds were screened for anti-tubercular activity in Maratha Mandal's Central Research Laboratory, Belgaum, Karnataka.

Procedure: The anti-mycobacterial activity of compounds were assessed against *M.tuberculosis* using Microplate Alamar Blue Assay (MABA). This methodology is non-toxic, uses a thermally stable reagent, and shows a good correlation with proportional and BACTEC radiometric methods. To the outer perimeter of sterile 96 well plates, 200µl of sterile deionized water was added to minimize evaporation of medium in the test wells during incubation. The 96 well plates received 100µl of the Middlebrook 7H9 broth (inoculated with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* of H37RV Strain) and serial dilution of compounds were made directly on

the plate. The final drug concentrations tested were 100 to 0.2 µg/ml. Plates were covered and sealed with parafilm and incubated at 37°C for five days. After this time, 25µl of freshly prepared 1:1 mixture of Alamar Blue reagent and 10% tween 80 was added to the plate and incubated for 24 hours. A blue colour in the well was interpreted as no bacterial growth, and pink colour was scored as growth. The MIC was defined as the lowest drug concentration which prevented the colour change from blue to pink.^[21]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase I: *In Silico* Studies

1. Drug Target Selection

CID 32030

Figure 1: a) Binding of ligands with 2B35.pdb b) best fitted lead

By analysing the results, compound CID 32030 containing pyrazole, thiazole nucleus were found to have good fitness values-89.16 (2B35.pdb) -98.53

(1UZN.pdb) -68.94 (4BFZ.pdb). Therefore, based on the virtual screening and from literature, pyrazole, thiazole was identified as a lead.

Figure 2: Structure of designed lead-Pyrazolyl Thiazole derivatives (PTH 1-10)

3. Lead Optimization

Computation of drug like properties of designed ligands

The drug-likeness properties and oral bioavailability profile were analysed by utilizing the Lipinski filter in the molinspiration server. The results are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2: Drug likeness screening of ligands (PTH₁₋₁₀) by molinspiration

S. No	Compound Code	Molecular Weight g/Mol	No. of H Bond Acceptors	No. of H Bond Donors	Log P	Rule of five
1	PTH1	397.494	4	0	5.558	1
2	PTH2	442.491	5	0	4.795	0
3	PTH3	476.390	4	0	6.122	1
4	PTH4	431.939	4	0	6.067	1
5	PTH5	449.929	4	0	6.259	1
6	PTH6	425.547	4	0	5.751	1
7	PTH7	415.484	4	0	5.803	1
8	PTH8	427.520	5	0	5.652	1
9	PTH9	411.520	4	0	5.880	1
10	PTH10	441.503	6	1	4.929	1

The ADME prediction studies were performed using Schrodinger Maestro v13.1, QikProp software for evaluating Caco-2 cell permeability, MDCK cell permeability, gastrointestinal absorption, blood brain

barrier permeation, skin permeation, etc. Which covers the entire ADME characters of the designed drug and the results are tabulated below.

Table 3: Drug likeness screening of ligands (PTH₁₋₁₀) by qikprop

COMPOUND CODE	Qplog HERG	QPPCaco	QPP MDCK	CNS	QPlogBB	QPlog Kp	QPlog Khsa
PTH 1	-6.817	3720.882	3170.941	1	0.213	-0.488	0.980
PTH 2	-6.759	438.795	313.897	-1	-0.846	-2.407	0.881
PTH 3	-6.744	3658.281	8269.431	1	0.385	-0.681	1.129
PTH 4	-6.754	3756.856	7886.474	1	0.383	-0.643	1.108
PTH 5	-6.603	3685.682	10000.00	2	0.468	-0.763	1.148
PTH 6	-5.872	4348.144	4081.752	1	0.325	-0.684	1.082
PTH 7	-6.708	3770.121	5800.712	1	0.330	-0.604	1.027
PTH 8	-6.821	3836.051	3263.333	1	0.150	-0.542	0.964
PTH 9	-6.727	3755.332	3198.170	1	0.205	-0.679	1.152
PTH 10	-4.923	95.340	76.664	-1	-0.914	-2.550	0.688

The newly designed compounds exhibited optimum ADME values. The leads were found to have good oral absorption, intestinal absorption, skin permeation and CNS activity. Hence, the designed compounds may show good oral bioavailability.

4. Network Pharmacology Analysis

a. Identification of Common Targets

The overlapping targets between compound-related proteins and tuberculosis-associated genes were

identified using the Venny 2.1 platform. A total of 32 overlapping targets were obtained for PTH1

respectively, indicating their potential involvement in disease modulation.

Figure3: Venn diagram showing overlapping targets between compounds and tuberculosis related genes.

b. Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) Network Analysis

To understand the functional relationships among the identified targets, a protein–protein interaction (PPI) network was constructed using the STRING database (version 12.0). The generated network demonstrated a highly interconnected system of proteins, suggesting that the synthesized compounds act through a multi-

target mechanism rather than a single target. Further analysis was performed using Cytoscape software, where hub genes were identified based on topological parameters using the CytoHubba plugin. Key hub genes such as STAT3, HIF1A, PTGS2, MMP2, and MDM2 were identified, indicating their critical roles in immune regulation and inflammatory responses associated with tuberculosis.

Figure 4a) Protein-protein interaction network. b) Top 10 hub genes identified using the MCC algorithm in the CytoHubba plugin of Cytoscape.

GO and KEGG Pathway Enrichment Analysis

Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway enrichment analyses were carried out using the ShinyGO platform

to explore the biological significance of the identified targets. GO analysis classified the targets into Biological Process (BP), Molecular Function (MF), and Cellular Component (CC), revealing significant enrichment in immune response, interleukin-mediated signalling, and protein phosphorylation processes.

KEGG pathway analysis indicated that the targets are involved in multiple signalling pathways related to host immune response, inflammation, and cellular survival. These pathways play a crucial role in the pathogenesis and progression of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* infection.

Figure5: KEGG pathway enrichment analysis.

Figure 6: Gene Ontology enrichment analysis showing Biological Process (BP), Molecular Function (MF), and Cellular Component (CC).

5. Molecular Docking Analysis

Molecular docking studies were performed using the Glide module of the Schrödinger Maestro suite to investigate the binding affinity and interaction patterns of the designed ligands with the selected protein targets. The docking results demonstrated that several compounds exhibited binding energies comparable to or lower than those of the reference ligands. For the InhA enzyme, the reference compound Triclosan showed a docking score of -6.146 kcal/mol. Among the designed compounds, docking analysis revealed that PTH8 and PTH1 exhibited strong binding affinity toward InhA, with docking scores of -7.802 and -7.668 kcal/mol, respectively. These compounds interacted with key residues such as Phe149, Tyr158, Ile194, and Lys165.

Similarly, docking studies against the MabA enzyme revealed that PTH1 demonstrated a favorable docking score of -6.321 kcal/mol and formed interactions with residues such as Arg25 within the binding pocket. Docking studies against the PanK enzyme showed that PTH1 displayed a docking score of -7.869 kcal/mol, which was significantly better than that of the reference ligand (-5.865 kcal/mol). The compound formed interactions with critical active site residues including Tyr182 and Tyr257. The docking results indicated that compounds PTH1 and PTH8 exhibited the highest binding affinities, suggesting strong interactions with the active site residues (Table 4).

Table 4: Molecular docking scores of PTH derivatives against *M. tuberculosis* enzymes

S.NO	COMPOUND CODE	DOCKING SCORES (Kcal/mol)		
		Inh A	MabA	Pan K
1	PTH 1	-7.668	-6.321	-7.869
2	PTH 2	-5.809	-4.846	-7.457
3	PTH 3	-5.269	-4.855	-7.588
4	PTH 4	-6.359	-4.889	-7.612
5	PTH 5	-6.680	-5.134	-5.015
6	PTH 6	-6.494	-4.684	-5.108
7	PTH 7	-6.208	-5.087	-7.632
8	PTH 8	-7.802	-6.300	-7.770
9	PTH 9	-7.104	-5.958	-7.673
10	PTH 10	-5.980	-4.851	-5.329
11	TRICLOSAN	-6.146	-	-
12	APO FORM	-	-	-
13	2-[4-(4-CYANOPHENYL)-3-{{4-(PYRIDIN-2-YL)PIPERAZIN-1-YL} METHYL} PHENOXY]-N-METHYLACETAMIDE	-	-	-5.865

Figure 7: A) 2D interaction diagram of PTH8 with the active site of InhA (PDB ID:2B35). B) 3D docking pose of PTH8 within the binding pocket of InhA.

Figure 8: A) 2D interaction diagram of PTH1 with the active site of MabA (PDB ID:1UZN). B) 3D docking pose of PTH1 within the binding pocket of MabA.

Figure 9: A) 2D interaction diagram of PTH1 with the active site of PanK (PDB ID:4BFZ). B) 3D docking pose of PTH1 within the binding pocket of PanK

Figure 10: a) Docking pose of Triclosan with InhA (2B35) b) Docking pose of 2-[4-(4-cyanophenyl)-3-[4-(pyridin-2-yl)piperazin-1-yl]methyl]phenoxy]-n-methylacetamide with Pan K (4BFZ)

6. Molecular Dynamics

The stability of the docking compounds were examined utilizing academic Desmond software and the protein RMSD, protein RMSF, 2D interaction

diagram and protein-ligand contact analysis were studied.

PTH 1 with Inh A

Figure 11: MD simulation analysis of the PTH1-InhA complex. (A) RMSD and (B) RMSF of protein individual amino acid. (C) 2D interaction diagram. (D) Protein–ligand contact analysis of the MD trajectory. Protein RMSD is shown in blue, while RMSD of PTH1 is shown in red colour.

The dynamical behavior of the PTH 1-Inh A docked complex over 100 ns using an explicit TIP3 model. The Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) of Inh A with PTH 1 seemed to range between 0.9 and 2.7 Å. The complex's RMSD value was around 2.1 on average. In ligand RMSD, a little variation around the 40–60 ns interval. On the examination of the trajectory, it was found that Benzene ring of PTH 1, which was freely moving, the main cause of this fluctuation. RMSF value is often utilized to access ligand induced alterations in the protein's internal chains. Protein RMSF plot analysis provides details about the flexible

area of the protein. As per the RMSF plot, compound PTH 1 made contact with 13 amino acids of the Inh A protein namely, Ile16(0.895Å), Arg43(1.033 Å), Gly96(0.901 Å), Met98 (1.072 Å), Gln100 (1.081Å), Met103 (1.623Å), Phe149 (0.559Å), Met155 (1.23Å), Ala157(1.540Å), Tyr158(1.53Å), Met161(1.090Å), Lys165(0.85Å), Ile215(1.76Å). The thiazolidinone ketone group made hydrophobic bonds with Met98 at 42 % simulation times, respectively. The trajectory study and overall MD simulation indicate that the hit compound will inhibit Inh A.

PTH 1 with Pan K

Figure 12: MD simulation analysis of the PTH1-PanK complex. (A) RMSD and (B) RMSF of protein individual amino acid. (C) 2D interaction diagram. (D) Protein–ligand contact analysis of the MD trajectory. Protein RMSD is shown in blue, while RMSD of PTH1 is shown in red colour.

Both complexes have been simulated using TIP3 model. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) of Pan K with PTH 1 seemed to range between 1.6 and 2.8 Å. The complex's RMSD value was around 2.0 on average. On the examination of the trajectory, it was found that the benzene ring of PTH 1, which was freely moving, was the main cause of this fluctuation. As per the RMSF plot, compound PTH1 made contact with 14 amino acids of the PanK protein, namely, Val99 (0.569 Å), Ala100 (0.679 Å), Met144 (0.960 Å), Lys147 (0.740 Å), Tyr177 (0.653 Å), Tyr182 (0.982 Å), Leu203 (0.642 Å), Tyr235 (0.642 Å), Phe239 (0.675 Å), Met242 (0.856 Å), Phe247 (0.991 Å), Phe254 (1.549 Å), Tyr257 (1.134 Å), Ile272 (0.777). The phenyl group attached to the pyrazole made hydrophobic bonds with Tyr235 and positive charge with Lys147 at 81% and 50%. The pyrazole ring made hydrophobic bonds with Tyr 182 at 77% simulation times,

respectively. Val99, Met144, Lys147, Tyr182, Leu203, Tyr235, Phe239, Met242, Phe247, Phe254, Tyr257 and Ile272 were among the hydrophobic amino acids interacting with PTH 1. The trajectory study and overall MD simulation indicate that the hit compound will inhibit Pan K.

Phase II: Synthetic Studies

Physical Characterization

All the ten new compounds PTH₁₋₁₀ obtained through schemes were prepared in good yield and evaluated by their physical characterization (Melting point and TLC).

Recrystallization Solvent: Ethanol, Solvent system: ethyl acetate: petroleum ether (3:7), Visualizing agent: Iodine Vapour

Table 5: Physical characterization of pyrazolyl thiazole derivatives PTH₁₋₁₀

S.No	Compound code	R	Molecular formula	% Yield	Melting Point °C	Rf value	UV λ _{max} (nm)
1	PTH1	-4H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	70	221-223	0.71	265
2	PTH2	-4NO ₂	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	65	231-233	0.62	271
3	PTH3	-4Br	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ O ₃ S	65	239-242	0.67	267
4	PTH4	-4Cl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ O ₃ S	75	237-239	0.73	258
5	PTH5	-3Cl-4-F	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ Cl ₃ FN ₃ O ₃ S	75	240-242	0.54	274
6	PTH6	2,6-CH ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	65	224-226	0.78	250
7	PTH7	-4F	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ FN ₃ O ₃ S	65	254-256	0.70	276
8	PTH8	-4OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	80	242-247	0.80	291
9	PTH9	-4CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	80	222-225	0.83	284
10	PTH10	-4COOH	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	65	263-265	0.64	304

Phase III: Analytical Studies

Spectral Characterization

The structures of synthesized compounds during the present investigation were established on the basis of chemical data IR, UV, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and MASS spectral data. All the spectra were obtained through the corresponding functional groups in the compound.

Compound code: PTH 1

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Solvent used : Ethanol

UV (λ_{max}) : 265nm

Figure13: UV spectra of PTH 1

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure14: IR spectra of PTH 1

Table 6:IR Spectrum of PTH 1

S.No	Types of vibration	Frequency (cm^{-1})
1.	Aromatic C-H	2919.7
2.	C=O thiazole	1692.56
3.	C=N pyrazole	1549.16
4.	C-N pyrazole	1365.21
5.	C-S thiazole	1174.44
6.	N-N pyrazole	1040.41

MASS SPECTROSCOPY : 398.78 ($M+1$)⁺ ion peak

Compound code: PTH 8

UV SPECTROSCOPY

Solvent used : Ethanol

UV (λ_{max}) : 291nm

Figure15: UV spectra of PTH 8

IR SPECTROSCOPY

Figure16: IR Spectrum of PTH 8

Table 7: IR Spectrum of PTH 8

S.No	Types of vibration	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)
1.	Aromatic C-H	2916.81
2.	C=O thiazole	1690.3
3.	C=N pyrazole	1548.56
4.	C-N pyrazole	1359.57
5.	C-S thiazole	1143.26
6.	N-N pyrazole	1044.26

Table 9: ¹³C Spectrum values of PTH 8

Type of bond	δ (ppm)
CH ₃	30.2755
Ar-C-H	119.6631-131.632
C=C	139.2177
C=N	146.1249

MASS SPECTROSCOPY : 430.21
(M+1)⁺ ion peak

Based on the docking score the compounds were selected and evaluated for *in-vitro* antitubercular activity by the Microplate Alamar Blue Assay method using Mycobacterium tuberculosis H37Rv strain ATCC No- 27294.

Phase IV: Antitubercular Screening

Microplate Alamar Blue Assay (Maba) Method

Figure 19: Antitubercular screening of PTH using Alamar Blue Assay method (MABA)

Note: A-PTH 1, B- PTH 8, C- PTH 9

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values for the synthesized novel pyrazolyl thiazole were observed and tabulated below.

Table 10: Antitubercular screening of synthesized pyrazolyl thiazole (PTH)

S. No.	Sample	100 μg/ml	50 μg/ml	25 μg/ml	12.5 μg/ml	6.25 μg/ml	3.12 μg/ml	1.6 μg/ml	0.8 μg/ml
01	A(PTH1)	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
02	B(PTH8)	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R
03	C(PTH9)	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R

Note: S-Sensitive, R-Resistant

The results shows that selected pyrazolyl thiazole (PTH 1, 8, 9) derivatives had shown excellent antitubercular potential. The compounds were found to inhibit the growth of Mycobacterium tuberculosis when compared to the standard, Isoniazid (**MIC: 1.6 µg/ml**). The compound **PTH 8** (-4-OCH₃), **PTH 9** (-4-CH₃) had shown minimum inhibitory concentration at **1.6 µg/ml** which were excellent when compared with the standard isoniazid with the minimum inhibitory concentration at 1.6 µg/ml. The compounds PTH 1 (unsubstituted) showed good minimum inhibitory concentration value of 3.12 µg/ml when compared to the standard. The dimethoxy and methyl group (-4-methoxy and -4-methyl) substituted pyrazolyl thiazole derivatives found to show excellent activity owing to its strong electron releasing nature. Thus, the designed pyrazolyl thiazole **PTH 8** (-4-OCH₃), **PTH 9** (-4-CH₃) derivatives showed excellent antitubercular activity.

CONCLUSION

The present study has proved to be a tool in minimizing the tedious process of drug discovery process over the traditional methods of discovery. The study integrates synthetic chemistry, spectral characterization, and *in silico* approaches to evaluate the antitubercular potential of pyrazolyl-thiazolidinone derivatives. The combination of network pharmacology, molecular docking and dynamics provides a multi-target perspective, which is particularly important in complex infectious diseases such as tuberculosis. Virtual screening was utilized for filtering the compounds and selecting the lead compounds. The *In-silico* ADME & drug-likeness scores of the ligands showed the compound to be promising as a good orally bioactive and pharmacokinetically feasible drug. The binding energy obtained from the docking study, the compounds PTH 1 (unsubstituted) was predicted to be the most active inhibitor of Mtb enzymes InhA, MabA and PanK. Molecular dynamics studies were performed in order to support the docking results and to identify the stability of the ligand-protein complexes. Various pyrazolyl thiazole derivatives were synthesized with good yield utilizing three schemes. The structure of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by melting point, TLC, UV, IR, NMR and mass spectra. The compounds were screened for

antitubercular activity which establishes the correlation of activity with the docking study. Thus, the designed pyrazolyl thiazole PTH 8 (-4-OCH₃) and PTH9 (-4-CH₃) showed excellent antitubercular activity.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization (2024) Tuberculosis fact sheet. Geneva: WHO. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/tuberculosis>
2. World Health Organization (2025) Global tuberculosis report 2025. Geneva: WHO. <https://www.who.int/teams/global-tuberculosis-programme/tb-reports>
3. Pai M, Behr MA, Dowdy D, et al (2016) Tuberculosis. Nat Rev Dis Primers 2:16076. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2016.76>
4. Zumla A, Nahid P, Cole ST (2013) Advances in the development of new tuberculosis drugs and treatment regimens. Nat Rev Drug Discov 12:388–404. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd4051>
5. Dheda K, Gumbo T, Maartens G, et al (2017) The epidemiology and management of drug-resistant tuberculosis. Lancet Respir Med 5:291–360.
6. Forrellad MA, Klepp LI, Gioffré A, et al (2013) Virulence factors of Mycobacterium tuberculosis. Virulence 4:3–66. <https://doi.org/10.4161/viru.22329>
7. Gfeller D, Grosdidier A, Wirth M, et al (2014) SwissTargetPrediction: a web server for target prediction of bioactive molecules. Nucleic Acids Res 42: W32–W38. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gku293>
8. Safran M, Rosen N, Twik M, et al (2021) The GeneCards Suite: from gene data mining to disease genome sequence analysis. Curr Protoc Bioinformatics 54: e94.
9. Hernández-Rodríguez M, Rosales-Hernández MC, Mendieta-Wejebe JE, Martínez-Archundia M, Basurto JC. Current Tools and Methods in Molecular Dynamics (MD) Simulations for Drug Design. Curr Med Chem. 2016; 23(34):3909-3924.
10. Hollingsworth SA, Dror RO. Molecular Dynamics Simulation for All. Neuron. 2018 Sep 19; 99(6):1129-1143.

11. Oliveros JC (2007–2015) Venny: an interactive tool for comparing lists with Venn diagrams.
12. Szklarczyk D, Gable AL, Nastou KC, et al (2023) The STRING database in 2023: protein–protein association networks. *Nucleic Acids Res* 51: D638–D646.
13. Shannon P, Markiel A, Ozier O, et al (2003) Cytoscape: a software environment for biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Res* 13:2498–2504. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.1239303>
14. Chin CH, Chen SH, Wu HH, et al (2014) cytoHubba: identifying hub objects in biological networks. *BMC Syst Biol* 8: S11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1752-0509-8-S4-S11>
15. Ge SX, Jung D, Yao R (2020) ShinyGO: a graphical enrichment tool. *Bioinformatics* 36:2628–2629. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz931>
16. Ashburner M, Ball CA, Blake JA, et al (2000) Gene Ontology: tool for the unification of biology. *Nat Genet* 25:25–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/75556>
17. Kanehisa M, Furumichi M, Tanabe M, et al (2017) KEGG: new perspectives on genomes and pathways. *Nucleic Acids Res* 45: D353–D361.
18. Chen Y, Chen T, Zhou L, et al (2022) SRplot: data visualization platform. *Front Genet* 13:978556. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2022.978556>
19. Essa Ajmi Alodeani, Mohammad Asrar Izhari, Mohammad Arshad, Antileishmanial screening, physicochemical properties and drug likeness of pyrazole carbaldehyde derivatives, *Asian Pac. J. Health Sci.*, 2015; 2(2): 41-47.
20. Thaker KM, Kachhadia VV, Joshi HS. Synthesis of 4- thiazolidinones and 2-azetidiones bearing benzo (b) thiophene nucleus as potential antitubercular and antimicrobial agents. *Indian J Chem.* 2003; 42B: 1544-7.
21. Evaluation of anti-Tubercular activity of nicotinic and isoniazid analogues, *ARKIVOC* 2007 (xv), 181-191. 2.

HOW TO CITE: Sonia George, Indhumathi S., Karthikeyan M., Thamarapriya G., Nandhini S., Gayathri Senbagam V.*, Exploring the Antitubercular potential of Pyrazole scaffold based Thiazolidinones: Design, In-Silico Evaluation and Synthetic strategies, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (6), 1174-1192. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21029947>

